

Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH: the organisational perspective

Work package 2 report

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April 2026

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19556098

Acknowledgement:

This publication is part of the project [Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH](#) with file number ICT.TDCC.001.003, which is (partly) financed by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) via the Thematic Digital Competence Centre Social Sciences & Humanities (TDCC-SSH). We are very grateful to Curie Wang for assisting in the data cleaning and transcription of the interviews.

Executive Summary

This report examines how Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research-performing organisations (RPOs) are implementing the FAIR principles from an organisational perspective. Drawing on a national survey (N=31) and seven in-depth interviews with research data professionals, the study identifies the current state of FAIR-enabling services, organisational bottlenecks, and opportunities for strengthening institutional capacity.

Overall, FAIR is moderately integrated into RDM policies, with 41.9% of respondents indicating integration “to a fair extent,” yet few institutions translate these principles into concrete roadmaps or maturity frameworks; results also highlight a lack of connection between technical RDM work and institutional strategic agendas.

Service provision is uneven across the research cycle. Data management planning is the most mature and well-timed service, while data curation, interoperability, and reuse services are frequently introduced late, inconsistently coordinated, or not offered at all. Interoperability remains the weakest area, with 41.4% reporting no services available. Interviewees emphasized that many FAIR-essential elements—especially I and R—are unrealistic for institutions to implement without support from national-level infrastructure.

A central finding is the fragmented governance of Digital Competence Centres (DCCs). Although DCCs exist in most institutions, they often lack clear mandates, stable capacity, or integration with key stakeholders such as IT, Privacy, Ethics, and Legal. This fragmentation results in reactive rather than proactive FAIR support.

The report concludes that strengthening coordination, embedding FAIR in strategic planning, and investing in capacity—especially for interoperability and software support—are essential steps toward a coherent national approach to FAIR implementation in the Dutch SSH.

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1. Introduction

○ 1.1 Background and Motivation

The **Untangling FAIR Implementation project** tackled FAIR Implementation from both the technical side and the organisational side. Organisational dynamics in Dutch SSH play an important role both as enablers of data infrastructure use that is developed at the national level as well as potential playgrounds for innovative FAIR-aligned research data management practices in SSH domains that can trickle up to national infrastructure projects and provide input for current needs and bottlenecks.

In addition, the continuous **NWO investment in Digital Competence Centres** throughout Dutch Universities provides a unique context that has not been explored in terms of its effectiveness in streamlining FAIR-enabling services within institutions and how these connect to national-level infrastructure projects.

From this perspective, we aimed to reach out to not only data stewards but **also team leads, coordinators** and **managers** whose task is to enable service coordination within the organisation and align relevant units, as well as to bring in recommendations and best practices from national initiatives and discipline-specific FAIR practices.

The current deliverable was designed with these two key elements in mind and sought to explore: 1) To what degree data professionals and the DCCs have organisational capacity, including policy and strategy work, to support FAIR data services within their organisational structure and how these relate to national infrastructure and opportunities and 2) To identify organisational bottlenecks that can be highlighted with the rest of the Dutch Data Management Community and contribute to a **National Action Plan** to mitigate these.

○ 1.2 Scope and Delimitations

While the organisational aspect of FAIR-supporting services is within scope, the technical limitations of infrastructure adopted by SSH RPOs is the focus of a separate Work Package within the project (WP1). In addition, while individual participants may have mentioned budget limitations or constraints, this Work Package did not inquire or have access to any budget considerations for FAIR-enabling services in any SSH institution that was approached.

2. FAIR Data Maturity in SSH

The FAIR Principles were designed to make research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. One of the key frameworks to evaluate the adoption of the FAIR Principles is that of the Research Data Alliance's [FAIR Data Maturity Model](#) for research data objects which translates the FAIR principles into 41 Essential, Important and Useful indicators that can be used to review an organisation's maturity towards FAIR. These indicators need to be in turn underpinned by services which enable their delivery.

A review¹ of the essential indicators for FAIR data suggests that the implementation of a number of the essential FAIR Indicators are not within the scope of RPOs as such but fall under the mandate of larger organisations and refer to metadata standards and well-established technical protocols, such as the application of standardized **http** protocol to access (meta)data, the minting and

¹ Appendix 1

maintaining of Persistent Identifiers for published (meta)data, whether metadata and data both resolve to a record with a persistent identifier, or that metadata is available even if the data is no longer available.

From this perspective, the duty of care of RPOs is to both steer researchers to repositories that meet these technical requirements while providing education and guidance, or acquire tooling that supports these same technical requirements for data archiving services that they choose to provide and build services and governance around these tools to meet FAIR and institutional and Code of Conduct criteria for the availability of research data.

Regardless of the institutional choice of having an internal repository (e.g., a Dataverse instance through DataverseNL) some FAIR Essential Indicators may be considered to fall within the responsibility of RPOs and their DCCs in the case of Dutch universities and not always related to infrastructure. These include,

- the provision of rich metadata to enhance **Findability**
- the inclusion of *Provenance, Accessibility, and License* information that ensure **Reusability**
- the use of *Community Standards* for data and metadata, also to support **Reusability**

In scenarios where the DCC would also be responsible for an internally managed repository, then the layer of institutional governance, processes checklists to ensure up-to-standard curation and archiving would need to be established.

In practice, very few of these FAIR-essential elements can be implemented by the researcher/user alone without the RPO having provided guidance and services that facilitate them. For example, License and Accessibility information, whether human- or machine-readable, crucially depends on institutional alignment and ability of the DCC and related stakeholders to develop reliable frameworks that can be used for research outputs, including data, which reflect both RDM and Open Science best practices as well as institutional policies around Intellectual Property, Data Categorization, and Research Integrity, among others.

This is even more prominent when taking into account Data Management Planning services, which are there to ideally ensure FAIR-from-the-start processes, and the role of first line and coordinating data stewards, for whom FAIR remains an ambition that is implemented outside of their institution.

3. Methodology

○ 3.1 Research Design

WP 2 was carried out through a mixed methods approach of surveys and interviews with professional staff across Dutch universities that work in Research Data Management support and service coordination or leadership. Detailed descriptions of each component are included separately below.

○ 3.2 Survey: Design, Distribution, and Response

The survey instrument [Appendix A] was designed to capture the current state of FAIR data implementation across Dutch SSH universities, with attention to organisational infrastructure, service provision, perceived barriers, and the relevance of FAIR across institutional strategy.

The survey contained included closed-ended questions (Likert, multi-select questions and matrix questions) related to maturity of policy and FAIR roadmaps, FAIR-enabling services, coordination and use frequency as well as bottlenecks and challenges for three stakeholder groups: Researchers, Data Professionals and Management. In addition, the survey included open ended questions related to barriers for FAIR implementation in SSH and how these could be addressed and the relevance of the FAIR Principles for SSH disciplines as well as for RPO strategies revolving societal impact and engagement.

The survey was administered online via Qualtrics and distributed through RDM mailing lists and social media. The target population consisted of staff directly responsible for FAIR-enabling service provision, information management and policy development, as well as team leads and management of these services across RPOs. Active researchers were excluded, reflecting the study's focus on institutional infrastructure and support capacity rather than researcher-level behaviour.

Recruitment proceeded through purposive sampling via institutional RDM networks, the national data stewardship community, and direct contact with data support leads at Dutch universities.

Responses were collected between February and November 2025. In total there were 87 responses. Following data collection, a completion-based inclusion criterion was applied: responses were retained if the respondent completed all or nearly all substantive items. Inspection of the Qualtrics progress variable revealed a sharp discontinuity in the data, with a natural break between responses at 95–100% completion and a cluster at or below 49%, with no intermediate cases. One response at 95% completion was included upon inspection, even as it had not completed the final substantive matrix question. The final analytical sample comprised 31 complete responses.

Respondents represented 11 anonymised Research Performing Organisations (coded Org 1–11), with respondents working at a faculty or department-level at 58.1%, n=18; respondents working in institution-wide roles at 38.7%, n=12, and one respondent operating primarily at a national level. In terms of role composition, 54.8% (n=17) were research data professionals, 32.3% (n=10) were in management or coordination roles, and 12.9% (n=4) were research information professionals. For the purposes of analysis, the latter two groups are combined into two analytical groupings: data professionals (n=21, 67.7%) and management (n=10, 32.3%).

Familiarity with the FAIR principles was high across the sample: 58.1% (n=18) described themselves as completely familiar and a further 16.1% (n=5) as fairly familiar, consistent with the professional profile of the target population.

Responses were included if progress rate was recorded as 95% or higher. In the dataset a 95% progress indicated that all questions were answered apart from the last matrix question and the optional invitation for a follow-up interview.

- 3.3 Interviews: Participant Selection and Protocol

10 interviews were conducted with RDM professionals in various roles in the RDM domain in Dutch universities between March and May 2025. The interviews were either held in person or online, recorded and transcribed. Due to capacity constraints we report only on the content of 7 interviews, with the hope that additional time will allow the inclusion of the rest at a later stage.

In terms of roles, 6 interviewees were individual contributors while 4 interviewees had a manager or coordinator roles.

The interview protocol followed three themes although the conversation was held open ended to follow the lead of the expert interviewees [Appendix B]:

- A. Institutional Knowledge: Interviewees were asked to talk about the knowledge they have of how FAIR-enabling services/RDM services are carried out, who are the key stakeholders and the stakeholder map, and how is FAIR-enabling policy implemented.
- B. Service coordination: How are services implemented across stakeholders (RDM, Privacy, Faculty, IT, Library) and what are some of the bottlenecks
- C. The Value of FAIR: Interviewees were asked how they see the value of FAIR and FAIR-enabling services for SSH domains and whether these can be connected to strategies for social impact and engagement.

4. Survey results

Respondents were asked to rate the extent to which their organisation's RDM policies integrate the FAIR principles. No respondent reported full integration; the majority (41.9%, n=13) selected 'to a fair extent', followed by 'to a moderate extent' (22.6%, n=7) and 'to a large extent' (22.6%, n=7). A meaningful minority reported only minimal integration (12.9%, n=4). When asked about the relevance of this integration given SSH-specific challenges, responses were markedly more positive: 52.9% rated it as quite relevant and a further 41.2% as moderately relevant, with only one respondent reporting slight relevance.

Integration of FAIR into broader organisational strategies for societal impact was weaker. The modal response was 'to a moderate extent' (32.3%, n=10), with 29.0% (n=9) selecting 'to a fair extent' and 12.9% (n=4) 'to a small extent'. Three respondents reported no integration whatsoever and a further three indicated they did not know, suggesting limited visibility of this link at strategic level. In total, 47.8% rated as quite relevant the integration of the FAIR principles in impact and engagement strategies.

Despite moderate inclusion in RDM policies, a high number of respondents reported that the FAIR Principles are not translated into institutional roadmaps or maturity frameworks for service provision. Only 6.5% (n=2) reported working in an organisation that has a framework with defined priorities and timelines, and 19.4% (n=6) had one but without clear priorities. A combined 74.2% either had no framework (35.5%, n=11) or were unsure whether one existed (38.7%, n=12)

Table 1. Policy integration, societal strategy, and maturity frameworks (N=31)

Item	Most common response	n (%)
FAIR in RDM policy (extent)	To a fair extent	13 (41.9%)
Relevance of FAIR–RDM integration	Quite relevant	9 (52.9%)
FAIR in societal impact strategy	To a moderate extent	10 (32.3%)
Maturity/roadmap framework exists	No or unsure	23 (74.2%)

A majority of the respondents (58.1%, n=18) indicated that their RPO hosted a Digital Competence Centre while the rest were either not sure (19.4%, n=6) or the DCC was not existing (12.9%, n=4) or not applicable (9.7%, n=3). In terms of organisations, respondents from 7 RPOs indicated clearly that there is a DCC present while respondent from the remaining organisations were either unsure or they indicated that there is no DCC in their institution.

The library is the most frequent unit responsible for FAIR Implementation, present in 9 of 11 organisations. IT services and faculty/department-level units are tied in second place while central professional services were in third place, mentioned by respondents in 6 RPOs. Two RPOs name only "Other" or non-library units, in line with the fact that these are not universities.

Many of respondents (67.7%, n=21) reported that their organisation offers tools for storage, access, and publication of research data developed or managed by internal staff. A further 16.1% gave qualified or partial responses, and only 6.5% (n=2) reported directing researchers exclusively to external repositories.

Respondents were asked to rate whether four categories of FAIR-enabling service are provided at the right stage of the research cycle, defined as follows:

- Data management planning (e.g., trainings, guidelines and expertise on data management plans, privacy, security, RDM costs, data licensing etc.)
- Data curation (e.g., advice or hands-on support for data and metadata quality, enrichment, integrity checks, etc.)
- Data access or publication (e.g., hosting a FAIR repository, data access assistance, data publication in Trusted Repositories with persistent identifiers, etc.)
- Data interoperability and reuse (machine-actionable DMPs and codebooks, enabling the use of controlled vocabularies for multiple data types, advice or hands-on support for sustainable formats, etc.)

Data management planning (DMP) services were most positively rated: 57.1% (n=16) considered them well-timed, though 28.6% (n=8) judged them somewhat late. (Table 2).

Table 2. Timing of FAIR-enabling services by research cycle stage (n per response option)

Service area	Too early	Somewhat early	Right time	Somewhat late	Too late	Not offered	N
Data management planning	1	1	16	8	2	0	28
Data curation	0	2	2	9	4	5	22
Data access/publication	2	0	14	6	4	0	26
Data interoperability/reuse	0	0	0	4	1	12	17

Data access and publication services were also rated as well-timed by a majority (51.9%, n=14). In contrast, data curation services were considered somewhat late or too late by 46.4% of respondents (n=13), with five noting they were not offered at all. Data interoperability and reuse services were

the least offered: 12 respondents (41.4%) reported they were not offered at all, and none rated them as well-timed. Overall satisfaction with service timing was limited: 51.6% (n=16) were neutral, 22.6% (n=7) disagreed that services were well-timed, and only 25.8% agreed or strongly agreed.

Coordination of services followed a similar pattern (Table 3). DMP services were most often described as somewhat coordinated (n=15), while curation, access, and interoperability services were reported as less well coordinated. Data interoperability services were again the weakest: six respondents rated them as poorly coordinated, only one as highly coordinated, and eight were unsure.

Table 3. Coordination of FAIR-enabling services (n per response option)

Service area	Not/poorly coord.	Somewhat coord.	Well coord.	Highly coord.	Not sure
Data management planning	1	15	0	2	3
Data curation	6	9	0	1	4
Data access/publication	6	9	0	3	2
Data interoperability/reuse	6	4	0	1	8

Frequency of service use consolidated again these patterns. RDM professionals reported that DMP services were most frequently used by researchers (frequently used: n=15; occasionally used: n=8). 13 respondents indicated researchers never or rarely used data curation services and the same number indicated the same for data interoperability and reuse services. Another 13 respondents indicated they they did not know the frequency of use of these services.

The survey contained 4 open text questions that inquired about:

- How to better integrate FAIR in RDM Policies given SSH-specific challenges
- Barriers to integrating FAIR to engagement and impact strategies
- Quality of FAIR-enabling service coordination
- Whether there is a gap between services most requested and those most needed to advance FAIR implementation in SSH.

In terms of areas for further integration of FAIR in RDM Policies, respondents identified three areas of relevance:

- *The sensitive nature of most data collected in SSH.* Respondents indicated that the implicit assumption that FAIR makes for data to be shareable (whether publicly or in a controlled environment) is not clearly matching with privacy compliance requirements, exemplified by responses such as *"There is a lot of confusion about whether personal data can be shared and under which circumstances."* Another respondent indicated, through a critical comment, that this would be area for growth, where FAIR-enablement in SSH could expand to meet privacy requirements *"Privacy is used as an excuse within the SSH to not work harder."*

- *The narrow scope of RDM policies* applying only to data but not to other output applicable also to software, archival data, image banks, or analogue materials. *"We also quite often have software as output. Here we could use more guidelines, expertise and infrastructure."* The diversity of outputs mentioned reflects the fact that respondents were not only members of university professional staff but also members of other SSH organisations, including museums.
- *A recurrent theme across the responses was the lack of clear guidelines* that follow high-level policies. High-level policy documents assigning responsibilities are seen as insufficient without concrete guidelines, tools, and worked examples. *"Better to integrate FAIR practices in guidelines. Just assigning responsibilities in high level policies won't affect practices that much."*
- *Interoperability* was identified throughout the responses as a key challenge for which to provide practical guidance.

In terms of barriers to integrating FAIR to strategies for societal impact and engagement, the following themes emerged from the open-text question:

- *Lack of Incentives and work culture:* SSH researchers are not incentivized to invest time and effort in making their data FAIR or learning about FAIR. *"There are no clear incentives for researchers to invest the extra effort required."* *"Lack of recognition and rewards."* This was also in some part related to budget cuts but also high work pressure and infrastructure immaturity. *"Budget cuts are a huge problem."* *"The most important barrier: added effort in terms of time and resources while the work pressure is already high."*
- *FAIR as Technical Compliance and not as Strategy:* Respondents indicate that FAIR is often perceived as a technical and compliance step and is not included in strategic conversations. *"FAIR is often seen as a technical or research issue rather than something that directly impacts society."* *"FAIR principles may be seen as too technical and/or limited to operations."* In addition, impact is perceived as a communication and strategy effort from RPOs and is separate from technical conversations. *"FAIR is mostly considered in terms of scientific impact. Scientific and societal impact are often treated separately."*
- *Misunderstanding or critical attitudes FAIR from SSH Disciplines:* Respondents also indicate that within the disciplines itself the value of FAIR is not articulated enough even within scientific impact. SSH researchers are not clear in some cases that they work with what is for FAIR purposes considered data, while others do not abide by the explicitness that FAIR assigns to work in humanities that traditionally is carried out in interpretive frameworks. In addition, ethically FAIR is seen as insufficient and respondents indicate that CARE should also be part of the conversation in SSH domains.
- Respondents identified the value of FAIR for societal impact an engagement in enabling reproducibility, research efficiency and the public value of oral histories and archives being made open and accessible

In terms of the quality of FAIR-enabling service coordination, the following themes emerged:

- *FAIR support is fragmented across multiple organisational units without a clear governance structure to coordinate them. "Support, policy-creation and governance is fragmented across many different organisational units." "The DCC also has no clear governance."*
- *Even when there is coordination at the institutional level, there is variation at the faculty level in terms of service provision. This depends on whether a faculty has a dedicated data steward with adequate time and resources, which creates a tiered system with some faculties steering developments more than others "There are substantial differences between faculties... largely tied into the variable availability of a decentral data steward."*
- *FAIR-enabling services are reactive and they tend to researchers only when these come forward themselves. "We can only help researchers that come to us for help. Many don't come at all or come too late." "Something in the middle of the process would be very welcome."*
- *Coordination would be easier with infrastructure maturity. In addition to fragmented governance respondents identify lack of tooling to coordinate workflows across the research cycle for FAIR-enablement. "We want to coordinate this with a workflow tool, but don't have it yet." "Many links are still missing to close the research cycle."*
- *Coordination is successful locally. Respondents indicate that coordination with immediate colleagues for a narrow part of the research cycle works well, for example Data Management Planning, Ethics, and Privacy.*

In terms of a gap between most frequently asked services and those most needed for FAIR implementation, the following themes emerge:

- Data management support is the most established service. However, follow through for what is declared at that stage of the research is lacking. *"There's nothing in place to monitor, incentivize, or enforce responsible data sharing."* In addition, respondents indicate that timing is also important, suggesting that early support is desirable especially because of lack of a follow through. *"I wish researchers came for support in the early planning stages." "Not enough support in the early phases."*
- Gap in research software support is becoming more important. FAIR-enablement, especially in the active research phase, requires software support, which respondents identified as lacking. *"For software more services are needed." "SSH communities taking into consideration FAIR principles for research software."*
- Lack of visibility of services determines frequency of request. Respondents indicate that researchers are not sufficiently aware that these services exist, what they entail and how they can use them to their benefit, beyond compliance. *"Services are not clear yet and most people don't know they need services and support."*

5. Interview results

Interviews across various roles in the FAIR-enabling services ecosystem in Dutch RPOs reveal similar themes but with more depth. To report on the themes we will be using the thematic framework that was adopted during the interviews as well, specifically:

- A. Topic 1: FAIR-enabling services, relevant stakeholders, and policy implementation
- B. Topic 2: Service coordination and related bottlenecks
- C. The value of FAIR for SSH and its connection to social impact and engagement.

FAIR enabling services were described by respondents as relating in large part to advice given by data stewards and by library specialists for publication purposes. In terms of data stewardship services, what was prominent across most organisations was the variability in data stewardship capacity across the various faculties. Subject 1 describes 16 faculty data stewards but allocated fte-s vary from almost zero (about 40 hours per year) to full-time data stewards that also have student assistants. In effect the former group of data stewards serve as contact points to central data management or related services and follow a minimal workflow for advice. Subject 2 also noted a similarly uneven picture, both in terms of capacity but also in terms of the teams in which data stewards are embedded. Some data stewards are part of information management teams, others in libraries, policy units doing mostly policy work, while others still embedded in faculties where the line between data management advice and privacy advice is blurred. From this perspective advice may also be uneven. Subject 7 describes managing the uneven capacity by adopting capability-based models where multidisciplinary teams across units are brought together to tackle one aspect of the research cycle in order to minimize variation in advice.

5.1. FAIR-enabling services, relevant stakeholders, and policy implementation

In terms of embedding FAIR in RDM policies, all subjects acknowledge that at present, FAIR is not sufficiently embedded in policy. Subject 1 describes that they addressed this by developing a faculty RDM policy template that clarified a lot of concrete choices that lead to the generation of FAIR data (e.g., which repository to use, when data can be closed or open). Subject 3 argues that FAIR should have a dedicated space in the policy landscape through a separate policy or ambition document to help it become more visible at the strategic level. This is because currently FAIR is not understood as vital for the Open Science agenda at the highest levels. Subject 7 supports the idea that faculty templates may become useful in order to operationalize FAIR in practice. In terms of which FAIR-enabling services could even be operationalized realistically, subject 1 and 7 both indicate that F and A would fall under the mandate of the organisation and could also be made mandatory from a compliance perspective, while I and R need to be deferred to later developments, either in institutional or national infrastructure. While Data Management Planning is one of the most prominent FAIR-enabling services, these are not machine-readable in most institutions, so from this perspective, interoperability services are not realistic. Subject 7 also indicates that there are too many steps to walk to achieve interoperability and that the standards need to be consolidated in relevant international scientific data organisations or consortia and not be the domain of individual organisations. Subject 4 indicates that similar discussions are relevant for software interoperability.

5.2. Service coordination and related bottlenecks

The stakeholder map for FAIR-enabling services in the organisations of respondents was varied with the DCC taking a prominent but yet not consolidated role. All subject report the governance of the DCC as fragmented. Subject 2 indicates that the DCC in their institution was established

through a funding call that was not coordinated internally at the beginning. For this reason a lot of services that are supposed to be included in the DCC are currently running but in parallel and building parallel collaborations, also successfully. The primary challenge is the difficulty in coordinating across departments with different knowledges, capacities, and work cultures, both at the expert level as well as at the managerial level. At the same time subject 5 notes that the organisation of work through functional teams helps deepen knowledge but run the risk of remaining in place because there is no line management to help decisions move across timelines and build further development. Subject 7 indicates that working across departments also has the side effect of low capacity, which increases the difficulty to develop policy and clarify processes just because of a lack of time from the members of the DCC functional teams.

In addition to timing pressures, budget cuts are also mentioned by respondents as putting additional pressure on the time and capacity of professionals across teams, who are caught up between meeting the goals and priorities of their line management units with the priorities that are related to FAIR-service coordination. Subject 1 reflects that when the LDCC was consolidated in their organization and faculty policies were adopted it increased workload for faculty data stewards. Unfortunately that happened at the same time as announced institutional budget cuts, making resistance from faculties more structural. Given budget pressures, Subject 2 notes that more specialized FAIR-enablement roles, like interoperability community manager or data modeller roles would *"never come from central budget"* and that decision-makers prefer to push costs to the national level. Similarly, HR processes, based on subject 4 and 2, are another impediment to having cross-departmental roles. Given these pressures, most respondents feel that currently the reactive role of FAIR-enablement is the most realistic. The more advanced elements of FAIR, e.g., developing domain-specific vocabularies are not within scope for their organisation, unless, as Subject 7 suggests, a specific use case comes along from a large-enough project that can cover the costs for this investment. From this perspective, the investments from OSNL and infrastructure are crucial. Subject 6 observes there is variability in the availability of resources for data management and data stewardship. In some institutions this is acknowledged and supported, while in others, the question of whether data stewardship is a *"primary process"* is not as evident at the management level.

The LDCCs in most organisations do not cover critical stakeholders like IT, Privacy, Ethics, Legal departments. This creates a gap in coordination and alignment and increases the burden of data management professionals to keep up with the complexity of legal and technological changes. In some organisations (Org 2) the requirements around ethical approval, where many of these stakeholders would need to converge, is not in place. Some ethics committees require a data management plan but others do not. Approaches for how to solve coordination and clarity in task division are not yet clear. However, from the perspective of IT, Subject 5 questions why a university should have develop its own systems for research support when a lot of research IT services can be outsourced to national infrastructure, while universities could function in a more lean way to support adoption and implementation.

Data stewards are the key network of "problem solvers" that mitigate the coordination frictions highlighted above. They are widely praised and supported both by researchers and by professional staff according to respondents. Whether researchers or data stewards should be responsible for the implementation of FAIR-related advice is also a topic of divergence, highlighting the double role of the profession as advisors with varying hands-on expertise based on their own disciplinary background.

5.3 The value of FAIR for SSH and its connection to social impact and engagement.

In terms of the value of FAIR for an RPO's strategy for engagement and societal impact, respondents acknowledge that the domains are now more separate than they should. Subject 3 indicates that there has been push back to include FAIR, and even Open Science to a degree, as key pillars of engagement and societal impact. Subject 2 indicates that FAIR is seen as a compliance issue while Subject 6 indicates that the degree to which FAIR is understood and included varies based on the institutional culture and how clear the link is made at the higher levels.

Respondents note that from the perspective of SSH researchers, how FAIR is relevant to the impact of their work is not clear enough to them yet, and that *"if the how is not yet clear, then the why is a bit hard to sell."* [Subject 2]. Subject 4 indicates that SSH researchers often are not aware that they are producing software, largely because they do not associate analysis scripts with software. Given this conceptual gap, advocating for FAIR software is not feasible. Even when clear, it is not an uncritically adopted framework and from the perspective of first-line data stewards, pushing researchers in one direction or another is not conducive to the adoption of their guidance. In addition, respondents believe that FAIR is applied at a gradient and that is not a conceptual limitation but a disciplinary prerogative.

The larger gap identified in the value of FAIR is the degree to which it makes data reusable. Similar to interviews, respondents indicate that unless data reuse is a normal practice in research, and unless FAIR adoption is shown to increase data reuse, the value of FAIR will not be internalized especially by SSH researchers.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

Both the survey and interview reveal a number of findings that would be suitable for follow-up in projects or national initiatives. Some of these points also emerged as recommendations in the Action Plan towards FAIR implementation in the Dutch SSH².

Firstly, the DCC structure in various organisations is fragmented and does not include key stakeholders in the data lifecycle management. While advocating for an overhaul of the current DCC structures is unrealistic, the results reveal that more capacity devoted to coordination and streamlining of work in accordance with an institutional current ecosystem of departments, including Privacy, Ethics, Legal, and IT are seen as very valuable (also see Recommendation #1 in [the Action Plan](#)). A more advanced model was articulated by respondents with a first and second line of support that balances the unevenness of capacity and services in various faculties or departments.

Secondly, respondents highlight that current limitations only allow for a responsive approach to FAIR-enabling services. This responsiveness is both in terms of researcher demand, but also in terms of national funding and support, highlighting the less active roles that individual organisations can or are willing to take for FAIR implementation. At the same time, outliers exist and these outliers are tied specifically to individual leadership decisions and visions, rather than as part of a broad acknowledgement of the place of FAIR-enabling services within various institutions.

² Maineri, A. M., Lushaj, B., Pociūnaitė-Ott, J., Touber, J., & van Horik, R. (2026). Action Plan Towards FAIR Implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19128135>

Thirdly, FAIR is missing in high-level institutional strategies. This gap in understanding of how FAIR is relevant to societal impact and engagement – respondents mention reusability of data as a key element of impact (for ideas on how to tackle this, see Action #3 Make FAIR count in the [Action Plan](#)) – may broaden the distance between FAIR research data management and strategic ambitions of RPOs, even as most universities strive to enable AI-powered services and to adopt AI at various stages of the research cycle.

7. **Appendices** (attached)

- Appendix A: Data and Codebook
- Appendix B: Interview Guide